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The challenges of Sino-Russian alignment to the liberal international order in Southeast Asia

Julie Yu-Wen Chen^{1,2} · Monique Taylor¹ · Alfred Gerstl³ ·
Kristina Kironska³

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Abstract

This paper explores the challenges of Sino-Russian alignment to liberal international order (LIO) in the Indo-Pacific, with a focus on Southeast Asia. Rather than being based upon common interests or values, the alignment between Russian and Chinese interests is pragmatic and expedient in the context of contemporary international affairs. China is traditionally an important player in Southeast Asia, while Russia lacks significant strategic presence and influence in this region despite pursuing a range of energy and economic interests, for example, Russia remains Southeast Asia's leading arms supplier. Russia's calculus in the Indo-Pacific, and particularly in Southeast Asia is neither bound nor framed by Sino-Russian relations. However, due to the emergence of strategic competition as the defining feature of contemporary international order, Russia and China's expedient alignment could pose challenges to the LIO in Southeast Asia. To investigate these challenges, this paper provides an overview of China and Russia's respective relationship with Southeast Asian countries, using the cases of Vietnam, the Philippines, Myanmar, and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). Through the responses of these countries and ASEAN to the South China Sea dispute and the Russia-Ukraine War, the complex implications of Sino-Russian alignment for the LIO in Southeast Asia will be revealed and discussed.

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing body of research papers, commentaries, and policy analyses on Sino-Russian cooperation or partnership and its implications for the international order (Schoen and Kaylan 2014; Odgaard 2017; Steinberg 2018; Guan 2022; Shakhanova 2024). Experts do not always agree on this topic; while some express concerns about their shared geo-strategic perspectives and the deepening of Sino-Russian cooperation, others emphasize existing constraints that

Extended author information available on the last page of the article

limit the extent of their cooperation (Wishnick 2022; Kashin 2014). This paper contends that while Russia and the People's Republic of China (PRC, China) do not see eye to eye on all issues, they share a fundamental opposition to the US-led liberal international order (LIO) and “closed military-political blocs” (Putin quoted in Ghosal 2024). Although both Russia and China previously benefited from the LIO (Hodzi and Chen 2018), they now have strong shared interests in countering it and preventing countries from aligning closely with the US to promote this order.

Central Asia is widely acknowledged as a region where US influence is waning; here, both the dragon and the bear have carved out ways in which to exert their influence and preferences for illiberal order, while strategically avoiding direct competition (Chen 2023; Odgaard 2017). In contrast, there is relatively little focus on the challenges posed by Sino-Russian alignment to the LIO in the Indo-Pacific, particularly in Southeast Asia. This is largely due to China's established role as a significant player in Southeast Asia, whereas Russia, despite pursuing various energy and economic interests in the region – including being a leading arms supplier¹ – lacks substantial strategic presence and geopolitical influence. Southeast Asia stands at the forefront of US-China rivalry, yet the prospect of Sino-Russian alignment in this region is hard to imagine.

The focus of this paper is to address this gap and conceptualize Sino-Russian alignment, if not outright cooperation, in Southeast Asia. The primary argument is that the alignment of Russian and Chinese interests in the region is pragmatic and expedient, both within the context of contemporary international affairs and specifically in Southeast Asia.

In the next section we explain Russia's strategic rationale for engaging with Southeast Asia and its perspective on the evolving dynamics of Indo-Pacific politics. Following this, the paper examines the convergence of Sino-Russian interests in Southeast Asia and their joint efforts to counter US-led Indo-Pacific alliances and partnerships in the region. The fourth section explores Sino-Russian cooperation in navigating the South China Sea (SCS) dispute. The fifth part investigates the reactions of selected Southeast Asian countries and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) to the Russia-Ukraine War and analyze how these responses are influenced by Sino-Russian alignment. Finally, the paper explores the response of the US and its allies to the alignment between China and Russia, concluding with a discussion on the implications of these developments for policymakers in the European Union (EU).

¹ Despite efforts in Southeast Asia to diversify their sources of arms, Russia's “no-strings-attached approach” remains appealing to countries like Myanmar and Cambodia. For long-standing customers such as Vietnam, switching suppliers quickly proves challenging (Asian Military Review 2023).

Russia's calculus in Southeast Asia

Russian policymakers and thinkers have long grappled with the question of whether Russia should prioritize its relationships with the West or the East. The issue of Russia's engagement in Asia transcends policy decisions, being intertwined with the nation's identity (Wishnick 2017: 122). Geographically, Russia is partially situated in Asia, yet in terms of culture and tradition, it aligns more closely with European civilization than with any Asian civilization. Conversely, Asian countries traditionally do not regard Russia as an Asian or Asia–Pacific nation either.

Despite Russia's roots being closer to European civilization, Moscow has sought to engage more actively with Asia in recent decades. This shift became pronounced in the early 2000s after Russia recovered from its domestic political and economic turmoil of the 1990s (Baev 2018: 75). This Asian or Asia–Pacific dimension is vital for Russia's justification of the 'Asian' part of its Eurasian identity and its role as a bridge between East and West (Wishnick 2017: 122–3). This positioning supports the notion of Russia as a great power, with influence spanning from Europe to Asia (Wishnick 2017: 123; Lukin 2016: 573–4).

Under Vladimir Putin, Russia has intensified its diplomatic activities in the East. In the aftermath of the 2008 global financial crisis (GFC), the West was perceived as in decline and Russia's shifted its energy strategy towards the Asian market to reduce dependence on the European market and capitalize on Asia's rising energy demands (Putin 2011). In 2009, Russia completed the East Siberian Pacific Ocean pipeline, expanding energy relations with China, Japan and Southeast Asian countries such as Indonesia and the Philippines (Wishnick 2017: 124). In 2010, Putin openly expressed his interests in the East, aligning domestic policies aimed at developing eastern territories such as Siberia, the Far East, and Vladivostok through economic engagement with neighbouring countries (Huan and Thambipillai 2022: 203). After the West imposed sanctions on Russia following the annexation of Crimea, Russia sought to reduce its economic dependence on the West without completely severing ties, by emphasizing its "pivot" to the Asia–Pacific region (Lukin 2016: 576).²

In response to the GFC, Putin and former Kazakhstani president Nursultan Nazarbayev prompted the birth of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) (Putin 2011), which eventually came into reality in 2015. Their rationale stemmed from the belief that Western-led globalization had stagnated. To assist smaller post-Soviet states in integrating into the global economy, Putin and Nazarbayev advocated starting with regional integration, with aspirations to elevate their collective influence in global governance structures (Putin 2011).

A critical factor for the EAEU's success and integration into the global economy is Russia's strategic connection to the East, especially given that several Central Asian countries are landlocked. Russia is the only member state with maritime

² As China and India refuse to pay market prices for Russian energy, the European market is still of importance for Russia. For example, Austria still imports more than 90% of gas from Russia (Kurmayer 2024).

access hence, Russia provided Central Asian countries with access to the sea, facilitating their connectivity to global markets. This imperative prompted Russia to further pivot to Asia within the framework of its Greater Eurasia vision (Administration of the President of the Russian Federation 2019). However, these efforts faced challenges due to Western sanctions imposed on Russia following the Annexation of Crimea in 2014, which led Russia to implement retaliatory measures. Despite these obstacles, Moscow continued to pursue regional leadership and expand its initiatives by establishing forums such as EAEU+ with countries like Vietnam, Iran, and Israel, and promoting the Greater Eurasian Partnership that includes China, Pakistan, Iran, and India (Denisov et al. 2021:80–81). Nearly one year after Russia attacked Ukraine in February 2022, Russia outlined its 2023 Foreign Policy Concept, asserting itself as a “Eurasian and Euro-Pacific power”.

This 2023 policy concept clearly states that China is important for Russia in its “Eurasia” part. This can be read as China’s importance for Russia in Central Asia, but even more so, it should be read as China’s importance for Russia in its ambition to be a true Eurasian power. Being a true Eurasian power implies that Russia’s influence extends into the Asia–Pacific as well.

Here the importance of China is even more evident. With China’s endorsement, Russia can thus be accepted as a credible player in the Asia–Pacific region, despite reservations from Japan and the United States about Moscow’s involvement (Wishnick 2022). China’s ongoing support for Russia’s participation in the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF) and Asia–Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) illustrates this dynamic (Bilveer 1998: 496).

This does not mean, however, that Russia’s relationship with Asian-Pacific countries is couched in Sino-Russian relations. In reality, Moscow has actively cultivated ties with Japan (albeit strained by the unresolved territorial Kuril Islands dispute), North Korea, South Korea, South Asia and Southeast Asian countries (Kashin 2014; Somerville and Crawford 2023). These efforts are part of Russia’s vision for the Greater Eurasian partnership community (President of Russia Website 2016). The fact that there are countries in the region, such as Vietnam and Laos, that still adhere to Marxist ideology, also emboldens Moscow (despite Russia no longer being Marxist), due to their shared historical and political connections (Huan and Thambipillai 2022: 203).

Russia has its own economic and security policies toward various Asia–Pacific nations, emphasizing economic relations over geopolitical and security issues – a departure from the strong geopolitical and geoeconomic interests of the US and China in the region. Over the past decade, Russia has increasingly focused on Southeast Asia and ASEAN. Economically, Russia remains one of ASEAN’s smallest trading partners, yet Southeast Asian states have surprisingly purchased more Russian arms than Indian and Chinese weapons combined (Storey 2021:4; Huan and Thambipillai 2022: 205–206), contributing to challenges such as weapon trafficking.

In sum, Russia’s calculus in the Indo-Pacific, particularly in Southeast Asia, is neither bound nor framed by Sino-Russian relations. However, given the rise of strategic competition as the defining feature of contemporary international order, Russia and China expediently align themselves in various ways to engage with Southeast Asian countries, some of which can be seen as US partners (e.g. the Philippines).

The next section examines the convergence of Sino-Russian interests in Southeast Asia.

Convergence of Sino-Russian interests in Southeast Asia

Russia's presence in Southeast Asia is less pronounced compared to China. Moscow primarily focuses on expanding bilateral military and economic ties with individual Southeast Asian states, sometimes competing with China for arms sales.

Southeast Asia has traditionally been the forefront for US-China rivalry. China has expressed apprehension for decades over the prospect of a US-led Asian security network, viewing it as inherently anti-China (Chen et al. 2024). In contrast, Russia, as a non-traditional Indo-Pacific player, perceives its relations with Asian countries as less constrained by US-led geopolitical frameworks (Denisov et al. 2021: 81). However, Russia harbours concerns that the US-led Indo-Pacific alliance under formation and currently perceived as anti-China, could eventually undermine its plans for cooperation in the Eurasian region.

Like Beijing, Moscow rejects the security-based US vision of the Indo-Pacific concept (Huan and Thambipillai 2022: 210; Chen et al. 2024). However, in contrast to Beijing, Moscow is more amenable to flexible interpretations promoted by the other players, such as Tokyo's multilateral vision for a rules-based Indo-Pacific region. Officially, though, the Kremlin has not embraced the Indo-Pacific as a new geopolitical construct to replace the established Asia-Pacific framework (Denisov et al. 2021: 80). Both China and Russia see the Indo-Pacific concept as undermining ASEAN's leadership and centrality (Huan and Thambipillai 2022: 202; Chen et al. 2024). At the heart of this concern is the shared apprehension that US-led Indo-Pacific alliances are perceived as inherently anti-China (Denisov et al. 2021:80).

Russia and China similarly oppose the expansion of the Western-led North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO). They allegedly fear that the security dimension of the US-led Indo-Pacific alliances may eventually develop into an "Asian NATO" (Tass 2022). Furthermore, Russia advocates for a multipolar world order and thus resists American unilateralism and US-centric geopolitical alliances.

For these reasons, Moscow and Beijing find common cause in Southeast Asia by resisting the LIO, along with the bilateral and minilateral security alliances and partnerships that have been established by the US. While their cooperation may not extend to every economic and military issue, both countries collaborate on a more abstract and fundamental level to prevent the dominance of the US-led LIO in the region.

China and Russia also took advantage of internal developments in Southeast Asia to advance their interests. For instance, during Rodrigo Duterte's presidency in the Philippines (2016–2022), he expressed readiness to negotiate on the SCS dispute in exchange for Chinese investments. Even though the Philippines is unlikely to jettison its traditional ally, the US, China and Russia have been engaged in various diplomatic and economic initiatives with Manila.

Another instance of Russian and Chinese strategic maneuvering to exploit internal developments involves the prolonged unrest in Myanmar. Both countries have long sought to diminish Western influence in Myanmar. China has supplied arms to the Myanmar military and various ethnic armed groups, particularly those near the Sino-Myanmar border. This has allowed Beijing to manipulate violence in border regions to suit its strategic interests, switching it on and off as needed (Chow and Easley 2015). Russia, on the other hand, seized opportunities when Naypyidaw sought to diversify its international relationships away from both Beijing and Western powers (Wishnick 2022: 132–135). Russia began to cultivate closer ties with Myanmar in the 2010s. During the years of top-down liberalization (2011–2020), as Myanmar was opening up, Russia's presence and engagement with the civilian government became increasingly prominent, particularly following the Rohingya crisis in 2017 when Western nations disengaged from Myanmar due to significant human rights violations. Concurrently, Russia openly developed military-to-military relations, hosting visits from Myanmar's coup leader, Commander-in-Chief Min Aung Hlaing, and providing military training to the Tatmadaw (the Myanmar military).

This dual engagement strategy proved advantageous following the Myanmar military coup in 2021 (Lubina 2022). Before the coup, Russian arms sales were the crux of the relationship. Afterward, Russia not only became the principal arms supplier to the military regime but also acted as a counterbalance to Myanmar's deepening reliance on China, which intensified in the coup's aftermath (Kironka and Jiang 2023). Following Russia's isolation due to its invasion of Ukraine, it moved closer to officially recognizing Myanmar's military regime as the legitimate representative of Myanmar.

Russia provides Myanmar with intelligence on suppressing demonstrations and supplies military equipment, including Yak-130 fighter jets and Mi-35 helicopters, which have been implicated in atrocities amounting to war crimes and crimes against humanity (Lederer 2023). Compared to China, Russia poses no threat of invasion to the Myanmar generals. Moreover, Russian military equipment is considered superior to Chinese alternatives and is sold without any strings attached. In contrast to China, which supplies both the Myanmar military and various ethnic armed groups – including those aligned with the pro-democracy movement – Russia exclusively provides military materials to the Tatmadaw (Lubina 2022).

Besides arms sales, Russia extends diplomatic support to the Tatmadaw, such as shielding Myanmar from United Nations Security Council (UNSC) actions. Russia rarely vetoes in the UNSC alone, often finding an ally in China. Conversely, Myanmar's military regime provides an entry point for Russia to Southeast Asia. In March 2024, ASEAN appointed Myanmar's military junta as the bloc's new coordinator for ASEAN's relations with the Russian regime (Justice for Myanmar 2024). China tolerates Russian engagement in Myanmar and ASEAN, viewing Russia as relatively manageable compared to any Western alternative (Lubina 2022).

Furthermore, both China and Russia have endeavoured to integrate Southeast Asia into their respective economic initiatives. China, notably through projects under the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and other endeavours, is developing railway connections spanning Vietnam, Laos, Thailand, and Malaysia (Gerstl 2022). In Myanmar, China resumed various infrastructure projects after a brief pause

following the military coup (Kironska and Jiang 2023). Vietnam is the first external free trade partner of the Russian-led EAEU, which is also exploring partnerships with other Southeast Asian nations such as Thailand, Singapore, and Cambodia (Eurasian Economic Commission 2023). The subtle yet tangible alignment between China and Russia presents potential challenges to the LIO in Southeast Asia. In the next section we investigate the contentious case of the SCS dispute to examine how Russia's historical alliance with Vietnam contrasts with its relations with China, particularly on this issue.

Sino-Russian alignment in the Context of South China Sea dispute: focus on Vietnam

Russia's strongest relationship in Southeast Asia is with Vietnam. During the Vietnam War, the Soviet Union and China supported the Vietnamese communists. However, relations between Beijing and Hanoi subsequently deteriorated due to territorial disputes and Vietnam's treatment of ethnic Chinese on its soil. Vietnam's 1979 invasion of Cambodia, which ousted the Khmer Rouge, increased tensions with China, while the Soviet Union remained Vietnam's key security partner despite staying neutral during the brief Sino-Vietnamese border war (Yahuda 2004: 72).

After the end of the Cold War, Vietnam and China deepened their relations. Today, Hanoi maintains amicable relations with both China and Russia. However, conflicts over the SCS complicate the China-Russia-Vietnam triangle. Russia remains Vietnam's main military supplier, providing a full range of modern weapons, despite concerns over Western sanctions and the quality of Russian arms in light of their poor performance in Ukraine (Storey 2024: 5). While Russian military supplies to Vietnam is not in China's interests, China's reactions are mostly declarative since it understands that Russia will not pose any security threat to China in Southeast Asia. China also tolerates Russian arms sales to Vietnam due to concerns that Hanoi might turn to the US for military supplies as an alternative (Storey 2021).

Another source of frustration between China and Russia is Russia's joint energy exploration with Vietnam in the SCS. Since 1981, the joint venture Vietsovpetro, now comprising Russian Zarubezhneft and Vietnamese PetroVietnam, has produced oil and gas in Vietnam's continental shelf, within some territories claimed by China (Storey 2024: 7). In June 2024, Putin and Vietnamese President To Lam (since August 2024 General Secretary of the Vietnamese Communist Party of Vietnam) signed new agreements on energy, petrol, and civil nuclear cooperation. The Russian-Vietnamese cooperation irritates China: Vietnam worked with Rosneft, a Russian company, to explore the Lan Do (Red Orchid) offshore gas field in Vietnamese waters contested by China. Despite harassment of Rosneft's operations by Chinese vessels, Rosneft did not cease operations but remained cautious of China's criticisms (Reuters 2018). In 2021, Rosneft sold its Vietnamese assets to Zarubezhneft, a move seen as a pragmatic compromise acceptable to Russia, China, and Vietnam.

While arms sales and energy cooperation can cause tensions between Russia and China, Russia generally remains rhetorically neutral on the SCS dispute, but with a tendency to agree with China. Despite signs of Moscow aligning closer to Beijing

(Wishnick 2022), its amicable relations with Vietnam prevent full support for China's extensive territorial claims, such as the nine-dash line (Kapoor 2021). Strategically, Russia, like China, criticizes interference by "extra-regional forces" (i.e., the U.S.), and attempts to internationalize the dispute (Tass 2024). This opposition aligns with resistance to the international legal arbitration initiated by the Philippines in 2013. In 2016, an arbitration tribunal of the Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA) constituted under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea overwhelmingly ruled in favour of the Philippines on the SCS dispute. China rejected the ruling (Ghiassy et al. 2024) And Russia also opposed it, arguing that territorial solutions should be found between directly affected governments. In May 2024, Russia expressed support for a Code of Conduct in the SCS among China and ASEAN countries, though it did not specify if it should be legally binding (The National Committee of the Chinese People's Political Consultative Committee 2024).

Joint military exercises in the Indo-Pacific And SCS, including Southeast Asian nations, have been held in recent years. The only Sino-Russian joint naval exercise in the SCS occurred in September 2016, coinciding with the PCA ruling in favour of the Philippines on the SCS. China and Russia conducted eight-day drills in "undisputed waters" aiming to counter "common security threats" (An 2016). Since Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2022, Moscow and Beijing have conducted joint exercises in the East Sea focusing on strengthening naval cooperation" and maintain regional stability (Yang 2023), which Japan, Taiwan and the US view as warnings.

Despite Sino-Russian alignment, Southeast Asian countries, notably Vietnam, exercise their own agency. In its relations with China, Russia, and other major powers, Hanoi has considerable leverage due to its hedging strategy (Gerstl 2022: 109–11; Ghosal 2024). China and Russia are aware of this and take each other's strategic interest regarding Vietnam into due account, interests which do not fully overlap. Acknowledging this, Putin praised Vietnam's "balanced position on the Ukraine crisis" ahead of his June 2024 visit (quoted in Regan 2024). This example demonstrates that Vietnam is neither fully in the Russian, China, or US camp.

In the next section, we proceed to examine the agency of ASEAN and its members, particularly in the context of the war in Ukraine. This war has served to exacerbate intramural splits within ASEAN, which are being further strained by the Sino-Russian alignment. The differing responses to the conflict, ranging from Singapore's condemnation to Myanmar's open support by the military regime, reflect the varying degrees of alignment and dependency on either China or Russia among ASEAN members. This division weakens ASEAN's collective diplomatic effectiveness when it comes to security dilemmas, which had already been eroded by ASEAN's inability to effectively and collectively address the SCS dispute and the Rohingya genocide in Myanmar.

Sino-Russian alignment and the Russia-Ukraine war weakens ASEAN

ASEAN is the key regional organization that shapes multilateral architectures and normative frameworks in Southeast Asia and the broader Indo-Pacific region (Yoshimatsu 2024; Allison and Taylor 2017: 6–7). In navigating the growing confrontation between the West and the Sino-Russian partnership, ASEAN members

have prioritized their national interests over regional consensus. When considering the responses of ASEAN members to Russia's invasion of Ukraine, Passeri (2023) identifies four sub-groups: pro-Western, strongly pro-Russia, pro-Russia leaning, and neutral (cf. Gerstl and Simalcik 2023). At the extreme ends are Singapore and the Philippines, both US regional partners that are "vocal critics" of Russia, and Myanmar's post-coup military regime, which has expressed its support for Russia's war against Ukraine, likely due to Naypyidaw's purchase of Russian arms and a shared anti-West stance.

The three states that comprise Indochina – Vietnam, Cambodia, and Laos – lean towards Russia for historical reasons and due to distrust of the US-led LIO. While Vietnam and Laos refuse to condemn Russia, Cambodia has taken a surprisingly hardline stance against Russia's actions, voting in favour of a UN General Assembly resolution condemning Russia's invasion of Ukraine and urging an immediate end to the aggression (Sochan 2024). Moreover, Cambodia provided de-mining training for Ukrainian specialists. Despite this, Cambodia maintains a close relationship with Russia with both sides committed to enhancing their relations moving forward (Sochan 2024).

Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, and Brunei have maintained a neutral position, in keeping with their commitment to non-alignment in international relations. This neutrality is reflected in their diplomatic actions, such as abstaining from UN votes and calling for peaceful conflict resolutions without directly condemning Russia. Hence, the varying degrees of support for, or condemnation of, Russia among ASEAN members reflect historical ties, economic dependencies, and strategic alignments, all of which has been complicated by the Sino-Russian alignment. This dynamic further erodes ASEAN's internal cohesion and ability to mediate regional conflicts. Ultimately, the differing responses to Russia-Ukraine war illustrate the challenges ASEAN faces in maintaining regional stability and, given the increasing divergence among the members on security issues, threatens "ASEAN centrality" within the regional security architecture.

Furthermore, if we take Sino-Russian alignment in the region into consideration when looking at the regional responses to the war in Ukraine, we can see further challenges in economic and security terms. Economically, as noted earlier on, Russia's role as an energy exporter and arms supplier to ASEAN states intersects with China's BRI projects, creating economic dependencies that shape foreign policy outlooks. The alignment pressures ASEAN countries to maintain favourable relations with both China and Russia to secure economic benefits, complicating their ability to take clear stances on international conflicts like the Ukraine war. ASEAN's security landscape has also been influenced by the Sino-Russian alignment through energy and military dependencies, namely Russian arms export as noted previously (although this has declined significantly over the past decade) (Storey 2022; Guarascio 2024).

In addition to regional economic and security ties, Russia has been a full Dialogue Partner with ASEAN since 1996, participating in the ASEAN Summit, ASEAN Foreign Ministers' Meeting/Post Ministerial Conferences, ASEAN Regional Forum and other ministerial-level meetings on various issues such as economics and energy (Huan And Thambipillai 2022:204–205). ASEAN's regional

arrangements provide Russia with positive access it would otherwise lack (Huan and Thambipillai 2022:202). Since neither China nor most ASEAN countries, except Singapore, have imposed sanctions on Russia, the Indo-Pacific is a more amicable environment for Moscow. Cooperation with China remains crucial for Russia both economically and strategically, grounded in mutual support and the ability to resolve conflicts through compromise (Dikarev and Lukin 2022).

The ways in which individual ASEAN members have responded to the war in Ukraine and the Sino-Russian alignment more broadly, influence the position that ASEAN itself has taken. While pursuing differing stances on Russia's war against Ukraine, ASEAN members are united in their desire to not irritate China. At the same time, Southeast Asian countries continue to hedge between China and the US in order to cooperate with both (Saha 2022). Taken together, this has resulted in an ambiguous, vague and muted response from ASEAN on Russian aggression, as evident in the official statements that were released in 2022. These documents simply stated, "The ASEAN Foreign Ministers are deeply concerned over the evolving situation and armed hostilities in Ukraine. We call on all relevant parties to exercise maximum restraint" (Association of Southeast Asian Nations 2022a) and later called for a ceasefire (Association of Southeast Asian Nations 2022b) but failed to condemn Russia or identify its invasion of another sovereign state and targeting of civilians as clear breaches of international law.

Final remarks

While Russia's influence in Southeast Asia remains relatively small and restricted to certain domains, this paper highlights the increasing convergence of interests between the dragon and the bear in this region. There is no formal political alliance between the two countries in Southeast Asia and their relationship can sometimes be competitive too. Overall, they have avoided conflicts and, in some cases, coordinate their efforts in engaging with Southeast Asian countries and ASEAN.

Importantly, Sino-Russian alignment and ASEAN members' divided responses to Russia's war against Ukraine create further schisms within the region that weaken ASEAN. Russia's actions in Ukraine set a "dangerous precedent" that is especially relevant for the SCS dispute (Saha 2022). ASEAN countries rely on a rules-based order and respect for international law and sovereignty as the guiding principles for maintaining regional stability and security. The equivocation of the ASEAN bloc, reflected in its official statements and which goes against its fundamental principles, can largely be explained by the pursuit of national interests in the context of the Sino-Russian alignment and the desire to maintain favourable relations with China. Arguably, this balancing act by ASEAN is unsustainable and, in the long run, compromises the stability and security of ASEAN. It could also diminish ASEAN's influence in Indo-Pacific security at a time when it desires to maintain its centrality but is increasingly being sidelined by the rise of assertive and decisive strategic minilaterals such as AUKUS, the Quad and the Trilateral Security Dialogue.

The US and the EU policymakers and analysts have taken the fluid and, at times, hard to capture Sino-Russian alignment more seriously as the war in Ukraine has

dragged on. At the 24th ASEAN-EU Joint Ministerial Meeting in Brussels in February 2024, the EU seemed to have been able to exert influence to the extent that the joint statement by the two sides indicate that “Most members strongly condemned the war in Ukraine” and that all participants agreed on “the need to respect the sovereignty, political independence, and territorial integrity of Ukraine” (Association of Southeast Asian Nations 2024).

US allies in Southeast Asia can help to restrain Moscow’s influence and Sino-Russian alignment, but this often depends on domestic politics and leadership. For example, former Philippine President Rodrigo Duterte, traditionally critical of the US, sought closer ties with China and Russia during his term (2016–2022). Despite meetings with Putin and shared criticism of US dominance, bilateral relations did not significantly improve. Moscow’s interest in arms deals with Manila was hindered by China’s critical stance on strengthening the Philippine’s defense in the SCS (Jennings 2019). The notable agreement to purchase 16 Mi-17 helicopters (USD 215 million) was cancelled after Russia’s invasion of Ukraine; the Philippines criticized Russia at the UN and was concerned about potential US sanctions against countries purchasing Russian arms. The new, US-friendly President Ferdinand Marcos Jr. supported this decision and opted for US helicopters instead (Gomez 2022). This demonstrates that the Philippines has agency in navigating a complex geopolitical environment. Southeast Asian countries and ASEAN are indeed critical to the future of the Indo-Pacific region. Hence, they should take a more proactive role in safeguarding the region’s stability and order.

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Declarations

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Authors and Affiliations

Julie Yu-Wen Chen^{1,2} ·
Kristina Kironska³

✉ Julie Yu-Wen Chen
Julie.chen@helsinki.fi

Monique Taylor
monique.taylor@helsinki.fi

Alfred Gerstl
alfred.gerstl@upol.cz

Kristina Kironska
kristina.kironska@upol.cz

¹ University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

² Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia, Mahidol University, Nakhon Pathom, Thailand

³ Palacky University Olomouc, Olomouc, Czech Republic